

International Conference on
**SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS
FOR RELIABLE AND SUSTAINABLE - FUTURE
STARS - 2022**

Volume – 6

LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE

Organized by the

**Deanery of Academics & All Science Departments
Bishop Heber College (Autonomous)**

(Affiliated to Bharathidasan University)

(Nationally Reaccredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC with a CGPA of 3.58 out of 4)

Recognized by UGC as "College of Excellence"

Tiruchirappalli - 620 017, Tamil Nadu, India.

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Proceedings of the International Conference on
**Scientific and Technological Advancements for
Reliable and Sustainable – future
STARS - 2022**

16-18 November, 2022

Volume – 6
LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE

**DEANERY OF ACADEMICS & DEPARTMENT OF
LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Bishop Heber College (Autonomous)**

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Tiruchirappalli-620017, Tamil Nadu, INDIA

International Conference on
Science and Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable – future
(STARS-2022)

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PREFACE

It is my pleasure and privilege to welcome you all for the three-day International Conference on **“Scientific & Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable – Future” STARS – 2022**. In the recent past, the world we live in, has been threatened due to environmental pollution, natural calamities, pandemics and other unexpected catastrophic situations, fast depletion of natural resources on account of undesired wars and desired extended sophistication. Owing to the above crises, to protect our only living planet earth, it becomes mandatory on the part of the academicians and researchers from multilateral disciplines of basic sciences, life sciences and computational sciences to pool-in their expertise under one canopy, thereby creating avenues for interdisciplinary learning and addressing issues on sustainability from a collective experience and a unified perspective.

Deanery of Academics and all Science Departments deem it a privilege and honour to host this conference during 16-18 November, 2022 at Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India with the generous support of the Management of the Bishop Heber College and a team of committed, skilled and vibrant fraternity from science streams.

Modern academic research involves multi-faceted approaches to solve scientific problems, wherein collaborations and integration of ideas are prerequisite to arrive at meaningful solutions. Hence, the central objective of the conference is to promote multi-disciplinary, interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary efforts in research investigations by sharing the expertise of renowned scientists across the globe. This conference creates a forum to discuss the practical challenges in near-future and science and technology solutions for sustainable development.

The technical sessions are being enriched by 27 renowned scientists of international and national repute, having interactions in three parallel sessions under the category of basic, computational and life sciences. There are more than 300 full papers across varied thrust areas which is presented in oral and poster sessions. The best oral and poster is honoured with prizes for each discipline. It is a great honour that Dr. Nakul Parashar, Director, Vigyan Prasar, Department of Science and Technology, Government of India, New Delhi, along with Prof. M. Selvam, Vice-Chancellor, Bharathidasan University inaugurates the conference. We are fortunate to have Dr. Mark Husbands, President & Chancellor and Dr. Philip Laird, Vice-President, Trinity Western University, Canada amidst us to offer a word of greetings and to ignite the interest of budding scientists highlighting the achievements and opportunities in the field of research.

To soar the spirit of science high, Dr. T. V. Venkateshwaran, Senior Scientist, Vigyan Prasar, Department of Science and Technology, Government of India, New Delhi offers the valedictory address. In a nut shell, this conference is aimed to inspire young minds to pursue scientific research, foster new collaborative partnerships and provide solutions for sustainability.

I trust that the conference will infuse knowledge, instill new ideas for collaborations and also encourage participants to embrace their own passion towards innovative research. Our sincere thanks to the invited speakers and delegates for their valuable contributions to make the conference a grand success.

I thank the Bishop of Trichy-Thanjavur Diocese and the Chairman of Bishop Heber College, **Rt. Rev. Dr. D. Chandrasekaran**, the Patron, for his benevolence. I owe my thanks to the Principal, **Dr. D. Paul Dhayabaran**, Chair Person for all the support and encouragement. My gratitude to the Vice-Principals, **Prof. Alagappa Moses** (Aided) & **Dr. J. G. R Sathiaseelan** (Self- Financed) and **Dr. G. Gnanaraj**, Bursar, the Co-chairs of the conference, for their sustained encouragement. I would like to record my thanks to the Co-Conveners, Organizing Secretaries, Joint-Secretaries and Scientific Committee members for their great support for the success of the conference. I also gratefully acknowledge all the sponsors and well-wishers for their wonderful support. I wish and pray that the conference would be fruitful and memorable to everyone.

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Rt.Rev.Dr.D.Chandrasekaran, M.A.,B.D.,M.Th.,Ph.D.,
Secretary

MESSAGE

Greetings to you all in the glorious name of our lord and savior Jesus Christ. I am delighted in acknowledging the International Conference STARS 2022 organized by the Deanery of Academics - Sciences on "Scientific and Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable Future". Heber family always remains firmly committed to venture beyond excellence. Our goal is to provide our diverse student body with exceptional education, instilling in young people a love of learning, the ability to think independently, and the confidence to pursue their dreams and goals.

It is indeed a great pleasure and pride for me to disclose welcome note for a thought provoking International Conference STARS 2022. Foremost I extend my sincere gratitude and profusely congratulate Dr. D. Paul Dhayabaran, Principal, Bishop Heber College, for his constant support and encouragement in all aspects and a grateful and special encouragement greeting to Dr. V. Violet Dhayabaran, Dean of Academics (Sciences), for all the pain staking efforts carried forward. My sincere appreciations to all the participants of the organizing committee for showing a keen interest in organizing a successful Conference and contributing new ideas and research findings. I wish them for their endeavors to spread knowledge.

Meeting several challenges, our organizing team is working very hard to offer you a one of the kind experience. The topic suggests that this conference focuses more on practical applications rather than on theoretical inputs on current Corporate World. I am sure that this conference will help in understanding about the ever-changing corporate world and the corresponding reforms in India and across the globe. It's an overwhelming joy to be a part of this conference which really deserves plaudits of praise. I wish the conference a great success. May the lord bless you by his abundant grace and may this conference be a milestone to reach many more successes in the near future. Kudos to the Heber community.

BHARATHIDASAN UNIVERSITY
(Accredited with A+ Grade by NAAC in the Third Cycle)
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Prof. M. SELVAM, Ph.D.
Vice-Chancellor

Office: 0431 2407048
Fax: 0431 2407032

M E S S A G E

I am happy to learn that the Bishop Heber College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli, is organizing an International Conference on "**Scientific & Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable - Future**" STARS - 22, from 16th to 18th November 2022. Research is the key to finding the ways to harness Science and Technology to fulfill the need for sustainable development, all round. Educating oneself with the latest developments in sustainable sciences is a good start. Learning sustainable development practices in the global arena and teaching others the importance of developing sustainable future constitutes an era of spreading the culture of sustainable management.

In this context, it is to be reiterated that, sustainable future is at the least means our drawal from nature daily/yearly, must not exceed nature's regenerative capacity a day/year, as the case, may be. Science and Technological Advancements (STA) have made profound development impact on almost every sphere of human endeavour, right from mid 18th century to date. Every phase of STA has shown spectacular shift from the preceding paradigm. One great feature of any phase of STA is that within it, many sub-phases got housed, with the latter ones significantly different from the earlier ones. As the variation got extensive, new STA phases emerged, perhaps. The succeeding phases of STA must help limiting our drawal from nature substantially well within the regeneration capacity of Nature. The world would be happier in this kind of paradigmic shift of human culture towards building Nature.

I hope the International Conference will be a platform for exchange of views and schemes from scholars from different nations on Scientific and Technological Advancements, thus creating a reliable and sustainable future for our younger generations, newer generations to come and hopefully enjoy a better earth, than the one now we are in.

Wish the Conference a grand success! Hearty congratulations to the Convener of STARS-2022 and the Organizing Team! Best wishes to all the participants!

Prof. M. SELVAM

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Dr. D. Paul Dhayabaran
Principal

November 4, 2022

MESSAGE

I am delighted that Deanery of Academics and all Science Departments of our College jointly organize a Two-Day International Conference on **“Scientific & Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable – future” - STARS-22.**

I congratulate and appreciate Dr. Violet Dhayabaran, Dean-Sciences & Convener of STARS-2022, Organizing Committee members and all the Heads of Science Departments of our College who lead from the front in organizing an International Conference.

I am sure that this event will provide a platform for all the members of faculty of different disciplines of Science departments to get an opportunity to present papers in their area of research and also for all the budding research scholars, PG students and all the participants to get exposed to the new emerging trends in Sciences and its applications in various fields.

May the Lord Almighty guide and strengthen the Deanery of Academics and all science departments for the successful conduct of this event and my wishes to the entire science fraternity.

PRINCIPAL

XAVIER RESEARCH FOUNDATION (XRF)

ST XAVIER'S COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS)

St Xavier's College, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli - 627 002, Tamil Nadu, India.

Fr Dr S. IGNACIMUTHU, S.J.
Ph.D., D.Sc., FRES., FNAAS.,
Director

DATE: 3-11-2022

To

The Principal
Bishop Heber College (Autonomous)
Tiruchirapalli - 620 017
Tamil Nadu

MESSAGE

Dear Organizers of STARS-2022,

Wishes and Greetings!

It gives me immense happiness to greet you all on this occasion of the conduct of the International Conference on 'Scientific & Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable Future' (STARS-2022) organized by the Deanery of Academics along with all the Science Departments of Bishop Heber College during 16-18 November, 2022.

It is heartening to note that this Conference will focus on multilateral disciplines of basic, life and computational sciences with the objective of promoting multi-disciplinary, inter-disciplinary and trans-disciplinary-research.

This will be a good platform to motivate young researchers. I am confident that all the participants will greatly benefit from this.

Let me congratulate the Management and the Organizers for having taken great efforts to organize this conference.

Let me also wish the conference a great success and all the best

God bless

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Former Vice Chancellor, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore and University of Madras, Chennai; Former Principal and Former Director, ERI, Loyola College, Chennai.

Greetings

I am happy that Bishop Heber College is organizing an international conference on "**Scientific & Technological Advancements for Reliable and Sustainable – Future**" STARS – 22. Education is not only gaining information, but it is transformation. Through Education, College prepares young people for their livelihood and their lives. I congratulate the principal and faculty members for their efforts and hard work in imparting sound learning and character-building in the past years. You have been sending out responsible citizens who would contribute to the country's common good. Bishop Heber College has produced great people and leaders who contributed significantly to the nation's building and socio-economic development. United Board's vision is whole-person Education which promotes intellectual, ethical and spiritual growth. Bishop Heber also focuses on the same vision and facilitates students to develop high empathy, appreciate diversity, enhance communication skills, and build self-confidence. I am sure this conference will create a forum to discuss the practical challenges in the near future and science and technology solutions for sustainable development. On behalf of the United Board, I congratulate the principal and all the members of the organizing team for the hard work and efforts to organize this international conference. I wish you all the best for your conference and pray that you will move from Good to Great in the coming days.

With Warm regards,

Maher Spurgeon

Consultant, Director

South Asia Programs, United Board.

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Digital Preservation and Conversion in ALL INDIA RADIO: Olikalanjiyam Tiruchirappalli

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Abstract: Preserving and Conversion of digital resources are most important and challenging process for information resource centers. Even though we living in the digital era, the processing of born digital materials have to be preserved without changing the originality of the material. Disentangling digitization from digitalization may seem like a nit-picky exercise, but they are very different concepts with very different implications. This paper discusses the digitization, digital preservation, the process adapted in All India Radio Trichy and the issues and challenges faced by the organization while converting digital material to another digital format.

INTRODUCTION

Digitization is the procedure of converting from analog to virtual shape, additionally referred to as virtual enablement. Said some other way, digitization takes an analog procedure and adjustments it to a virtual shape with no different-in-type adjustments to the procedure itself. Digitization is the procedure of automating current methods which might be manually or paper-based. In the state-of-the-art world, current digitization broadly speaking refers to file seize and scanning and digitizing methods inside the procedure of having matters done. Audio and video digitization use one of many analog-to-digital conversion processes in which a continuously variable (analog) signal is transformed, without altering its essential content, into a multi-level (digital) signal. The sampling process measures the amplitude (signal strength) of an analog waveform signal at equidistant timestamps and represents the samples as digital values for input as digital data

IMPORTANCE OF DIGITIZATION

Digitization will increase efficiency, it protects your information irrespective of what herbal disaster, theft, or loss happens, and it makes report retrieval painless at the same time as modernizing your business enterprise to present-day marketplace standards. The threat of dropping your information is expensive Digitizing records will save your organization money over the long term. Digitization increases efficiency, it protects your records no matter what natural disaster, theft, or loss happens, and it makes record retrieval painless while modernizing your organization to current market standards

NEED FOR DIGITIZATION

Digitization is of important significance to records processing, garage, and transmission, due to the fact it "permits statistics of a wide variety in all codecs to be carried with the equal performance and additionally intermingled". The proliferation of digital technology developments is making choosing the right method for digitizing assets an increasingly complex process for information organizations. This technology is a major breakthrough in the 21st century, but it is important to develop a strategy to fully assess the costs and benefits of moving forward with digitization. With the current state of technology, scanning from the original provides better reproduction quality for color materials and low contrast materials than scanning from the film. When the endangered original material is digitized, the converted form acquires curatorial master status which, in extreme cases, will have to replace the lost original. In this case, of course, the quality of the reproduction must be higher than what is necessary in cases where the digitized sub form only exists to improve the possible standard access.

DIGITAL PRESERVATION

Digital preservation can include a set of processes and activities that maintain data retention in digital formats to ensure continued access to information. Includes preservation of materials resulting from digital reformatting, data migration, emulation, replication, updating, and data appending. These preservation measures need to be taken due to rapid and constant software system changes and stressful software environments, deterioration of magnetic media corresponding to CD, DVD, PC hard drives, and various reasons.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Stephen Abrams (2021) Digital preservation plays a fundamental role within the digital continuity of individual, institutional and cultural memory. It's important for repository stewards and stakeholders to understand whether or not those activities are booming so as to deploy finite programmatic resources most relevantly, effectively, and productively. Whereas preservation trait has been subject to intensive examination, the complementary critical quality of success has received less critical consideration. This study appearance at however the preservation community ascribes aspiring to the idea of success through attitudinal norms tacitly embedded in domain discourse. These are recovered through qualitative content analysis of selected preservation policy statements that act as public affirmations of the repository service "contract" relating to place intention and reciprocal neutral expectation. Success could be a live of the alignment between anticipated outcomes and actual preserved state ensuing from intentional intervention. Communicological critique of the norms illuminates why the measure of success remains problematic and suggests avenues by which metrical apply will be increased to boost its critical power. This includes location evaluative prerogatives to include concern for the persistence not solely of authentic digital info objects however additionally legitimate communicative experiences.

Dyah Srirahayu (2020) Libraries mistreatment institutional repositories aim to manage and preserve digital content. As suppliers of digital collections, got to} be willing to face varied questions, particularly political questions, however digital collections will be developed and meet the wants of users in an exceedingly comparatively while (long-term use). The matter to face is that the age of the information carriers, which might solely be a minimum of ten years old, that the digital collections have to be re-copied to scale back the possibilities of losing the knowledge contained within the collections. This issue is one amongst the reasons for the digital preservation of the repository' digital collections, that are intellectual and cultural property, likewise as assets for the repository itself. This study uses the descriptive quantitative methodology with a sampling procedure with 100, respondents lacy in webometry. The preparation of the library for long-term digital preservation reaches the consolidation part, the guardian consolidates its resources for the event of long digital preservation. The factors concerned during this preparation are structure infrastructure, technological infrastructure and resources.

Fernando almeida (2020) COVID-19 has had dramatic effects on the world economy, businesses, and people. However, digitization is additionally serving several corporations to adapt and overcome this state of affairs caused by COVID19. The expansion within the use of technology in the daily lives of individuals and businesses facing this exceptional situation may be to testament to' the digital acceleration process. This beta study analyzes the impact of digital transformation processes in 3 areas of activity: work and social relations. The impact of digitization ought to be crosswise to every domain and can promote the emergence of recent digital products and services supported by the principle of flexibility. Additionally,' new ways that of operating will drive demand for brand spanking new talent, despite' geographic location.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To know the collection of AIR library.
2. To identify how the materials are degraded and to identify the ways to correct them.
3. To know about the digital preservation and conversion process techniques carried in AIR library.
4. To know the detail understandings of Magnetic Tapes and Gramophones records are Preserved and Converted by the AIR library
5. To suggest suitable suggestions and recommendations for the AIR library

AIM

To evaluate how the preservation and conversion techniques is carried out in ALL INDIA RADIO Library: (Olikalanjiyam), Tiruchirappalli.

METHODOLOGY

1. The research methodology adopted for the study is to observe whether the in (Olikalanjiyam) ALL INDIA RADIO library have the selected parameters for the study.
2. Observe the digital Preservation and Conversion software's used in Olikalanjiyam
3. The digital preservation methods used in AIR library.
4. Identify the materials getting degrade.

AN OVERVIEW OF ALL INDIA RADIO TIRUCHIRAPPALLI

Tiruchirappalli station of ALL INDIA Radio is one of the six pioneer stations in pre-independent India and the second station set up in the erstwhile Madras state after the first one at madras. it is certainly located in the state of Tamilnadu. it started functioning in a rented building on Williams Road in the cantonment area of Tiruchirappalli with a 5 K W medium wave transmitter at Tiruverambur. Shri C. Raja Gopalan the chief minister of composite madras state inaugurated it on 16th May 1939 Shri Lionel Fielden, the first controller broadcasting India, broadcast a message on the occasion. on 02.11.1962 the station was shifted to its present new own building on promenade road now called Bharathidasan Salai in the cantonment area. The 5 K W Medium wave transmitter was upgraded to a 50 K W M.W. transmitter on 13.06. 1931. this was further upgraded to 100 KW M.W transmitters on 01.01.1988.

DIGITAL PRESERVATION AND CONVERSION IN AIR TIRUCHIRAPPALLI LIBRARY: OLIKALANJIYAM

All India Radio is a mass media organization of the government of India, with certain set goals of functioning mainly for the dissemination of messages, besides providing entertainment to the listeners. In a developing country like India, the role of radio in the mass media is indispensable and inevitable. Also, the medium has the maximum reach to people

The AIR library has two kinds of material. That is Film and Non-film materials. As per the government rule, under the guidance of the prime minister, the digital India policy is applied in the AIR library. So, they convert the materials into Digital form. Programs in the tapes are being digitized. Important programs and all the programs are moved into hard disc also copied in CD also more than 90% taps are digitized. Digitalized recordings have been preserved on hard discs and CDs.

PRESERVATION AND CONVERSION PROCESS

Magnetic tapes Conversion Process

Studer A807

Conversion Steps

1. Put the Tape in the Turntable machine (Studer A807), then set tape into a proper method. Next open the Wave lab software
2. Play it, with the help of control panel
3. When the tape is rotating, the audio will be converted into mp3 format in wave lab software.
4. When the audio converted into the software, the audio will be edited manually
5. Finally finished audio saved in the AIR Database

1. Play Button

2. Recording Button

Control Panel

Volume Meter Adjustment

Conversion Process of audio used by Wave lab Software

PRESERVATION

In library and deposit science, preservation may be a set of preventive conservation activities geared toward prolonging the lifetime of a record, book, or object whereas creating as few changes as possible. Preservation activities vary wide and should embrace observance the condition of items, maintaining the temperature and wetness in assortment storage areas, writing an inspiration just in case of emergencies, digitizing items, writing relevant metadata, and increasing accessibility.

NEED FOR PRESERVATION

The preservation of cultural assets through activities that reduce physiochemical deterioration and damage while also preventing information loss. The prime objective of conservation and protection is to keep cultural property alive. Preservation encompasses the activities which prolong the usable life of archival records. Preservation activities are designed to minimize the physical and chemical deterioration of records and to prevent the loss of informational content

PRESERVATION OF PRINT AND NON – PRINT MATERIALS

Types of Print Material

1. Newsprints
2. Journals
3. Magazines
4. Printed books
5. Pamphlets
6. Scrapbooks
7. Ephemera
8. Single sheet material

Types of Non – Print Material

1. Film
2. Magnetic Material
3. Plastic Material

Problem faced

- ❖ Dust
- ❖ Air conditioning temperature and humidity
- ❖ Compact disk
- ❖ Lamination
- ❖ Winding
- ❖ Fumigation

DIGITAL PRESERVATION

In library and archival science, long-term digital preservation is a formal effort to ensure that digital information of enduring value remains accessible and usable. It encompasses the planning, resource allocation, and application of preservation methods and technologies, and combines policies, strategies, and actions to ensure access to reformatted and “born digital” content, regardless of the challenges of media failure and technological change. The goal of long-term digital preservation is the accurate Representation of authenticated content over time. The Preservation and Reformatting Section of the Association of Library Collections and Technical Services of the American Library Association defined digital preservation as a combination of "policies, strategies, and actions designed to ensure accessibility of digital content over time." According to Harrods’s Librarians Glossary, long-term digital preservation is a method of keeping digital material alive so that it remains usable, as advances in technology make the original Hardware and software specifications obsolete. The term “digital preservation” refers to preservation of materials that are created originally in digital type and ne'er existed in print or analogue form (also known as “born digital”) yet as those regenerate from heritage documents and artefacts (printed documents, pictures, images or physical objects) into pictures victimization scanners, digital cameras, or different imaging technologies for access and preservation purposes. Digital preservation refers to a series of managed activities designed to make sure continued access to any or all types of records in digital formats for as long as necessary and to shield them from media failure, physical loss and devolution. The Wikipedia defines digital preservation “as long-term, error free storage of digital information, with means for retrieval and interpretation, for all the time span that the data is needed for”, wherever “retrieval” means getting required digital files from the long-term, error-free digital storage, while not corrupting the error free hold on digital files and “interpretation” means the retrieved digital files, that is also texts, charts, pictures or sounds, are decoded and reworked into usable representations for access to human.

ISSUES & CHALLENGES ON DIGITAL PRESERVATION

- From the minute it is generated, digital collection content is at danger
- Technological obsolescence
- Integrity and validation
- New formats
- Scale
- Fragility of storage media
- Key Strategies Activities

Strategies

- ❖ Refreshing
- ❖ Migration
- ❖ Emulation

SUGGESTION

The Researcher’s suggest and Recommend to the All India Radio are;

1. Need more space for the collections
2. Create Awareness about the Library
3. Ventilation
4. Update the organization profile

CONCLUSION

Considering the role of libraries in digital information management it is very impressive that the media and special libraries are very much equipped with necessary skills to handle digital resources and manage to preserve even in technological shifts. The organization like All India Radio (AIR) are started to adopt new technological techniques to manage the digital shifts. The organization over the years have developed an array of tools, methods and techniques for the preservation of traditional print and non-print resources with the purpose to make sure that works of distinction and valuable information are organized for maximum utilization of resources. Due to the paradigm shift of Digital India movement the organization finds a new path to preserve the Indian heritage, cultural Music and various speeches of Indian Social activist and Politicians. While preserving and managing digital resources the organization also faces new issues and challenges but somehow, they manage to overcome by following modifications and innovative suitable for local digital environment and economical setup.

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